

The Use of the Rotating Pt-Electrode for the Microdetermination of Hydrazine with Potassium Permanganate in Fluoride Medium

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An amperometric method is described for the microdetermination of N_2H_4 using the rotating Pt-electrode vs S.C.E. and zero applied e.m.f. It is based on oxidation to N_2 and H_2O with $KMnO_4$ under the following conditions: Acidity 0.01–0.06 N H_2SO_4 in presence of 1% NaF and 0.05 N $CuSO_4/10$ ml; NaF: 0.8–1.5% (corresponding to 4–7.5 ml 2% solution/10 ml); $CuSO_4$: 0.013–0.15 N (corresponding to 0.5–6 ml 0.25 N solution/10 ml); $CuSO_4$: 0.013–0.15 N (corresponding to 0.5–6 ml 0.25 N solution/10 ml); Amounts of N_2H_4 : 3.7 μg –5.97 mg. The method is accurate and lower concentrations can be determined than with the potentiometric procedure.

THE polarographic behaviour of hydrazine at a rotating Pt-disk electrode in neutral and acidic solutions was studied in various supporting electrolytes¹; the effect of iodide on the oxidation process was also studied². Several titrimetric procedures have been carried out for the determination of hydrazine^{3–11}.

Kolthoff¹² studied the oxidation of N_2H_4 with $KMnO_4$ in presence of 4N HCl but the results were unsatisfactory. Cay *et al.*¹³ showed that the different products formed are responsible for these variable results on account of the transformation to higher valency states. Issa *et al.*, determined N_2H_4 by oxidation with $KMnO_4$ in alkaline solutions¹⁴ and in fluoride medium containing Cu^{+2} ions as catalyst¹⁵.

Literature is however deficient for a procedure involving amperometric determination of N_2H_4 with $KMnO_4$ and it is aimed in the present investigation to elucidate the conditions for determining microamounts of N_2H_4 by amperometric titration with $KMnO_4$ in fluoride medium using the rotating Pt-electrode vs S. C. R. as reference at zero applied e.m.f.

Experimental

Preparation of solutions: Potassium permanganate solutions were prepared by a method similar to that of Stamm¹⁶ and standardised with sodium oxalate¹⁷ (normality of permanganate solutions used is based on valency change of Mn^{+7} to Mn^{+3}). Hydrazine solutions were prepared by dissolving the Analar product in bidistilled water and standardised according to recommended procedure solutions of permanganate and hydrazine of required concentrations were obtained by appropriate dilution. Other solutions including 2% NaF, 1N H_2SO_4 and 0.25M $CuSO_4$ were prepared from the Analar products.

Apparatus and Titration Procedure: The amperometric titration apparatus used is shown in Fig. 1. The

Fig. 1.

attainment of a steady diffusion current was maintained by rotating the platinum electrode at a constant speed of 600 r.p.m. The reference electrode used was a saturated calomel electrode (S. C. E.). The hydrazine solution was mixed with the appropriate of H_2SO_4 , NaF and $CuSO_4$, completed to a known volume (usually 10 ml) with bidistilled water and titrated with $KMnO_4$. The diffusion current corrected for dilution was calculated and plotted against the volume of permanganate. The dilution correction is made by multiplying the current measured by a factor of $(V+v)/V$, where V is the original volume and v is volume of the titrant added.

Results and Discussion

Effect of Acidity: The effect of acidity on the accuracy of the end point can be visualised from data in Table 1. and curves in Fig. 2. Good end points are obtained at acidities ranging from 0.01 to 0.06N H₂SO₄ corresponding to oxidation of N₂H₄ to N₂ and water. At higher acidities, the end point is attained earlier as a result of partial reduction of permanganate to Mn(II), or to the partial oxidation of N₂H₄ to N₂H₂ higher acid concentrations i. e. $2N_2H_4 + MnO_4^- + 2 HF_2^- + 2H^+ \rightleftharpoons 2 N_2H_2 + MnF_4^- + 4H_2O$.

Fig. 2. Titration of 2 ml of 0.0932 N N₂H₄ with 0.074 N KMnO₄ in presence of 5 ml 2% NaF and 2 ml 0.24M CuSO₄. (total volume ~10 ml)
 A) 0.01 N H₂SO₄ B) 0.04 N H₂SO₄ C) 0.06 N H₂SO₄ D) 0.08 N H₂SO₄ E) 0.1 N H₂SO₄

TABLE 1 EFFECT OF ACIDITY

Titration of 2 ml 0.09324 N hydrazine with 0.074 N KMnO₄ in presence 5 ml 2% NaF and 2 ml 0.25 M CuSO₄ at different acidities. (Total volume 10 ml).

Acidity N H ₂ SO ₄	Vol. of KMnO ₄ consumed (ml)	Theoretical end point (ml)	Error (% ; ±)
0.01	2.53	2.52	+0.4
0.04	2.52	2.52	nil
0.06	2.51	2.52	-0.4
0.08	2.47	2.52	1.98
0.1	2.43	2.52	3.57

Effect of CuSO₄ concentration: Table 2 and Fig. 3, show the effect of Cu⁺² ions on the oxidation of N₂H₄. In absence of Cu⁺² ions, oxidation of N₂H₄ goes more or less to hydroxylamine through the uptake of 2-electrons. The addition of Cu⁺² ions, not only improves the end point¹⁰ but also enhances the oxidation to N₂ and H₂O which is catalysed by these ions. However, accurate results based on oxidation of N₂H₄ to N₂ and H₂O are obtained when the titrated solution is 0.013 to 0.15N with respect to Cu⁺² ions (0.5-6 ml of 0.25N CuSO₄/10 ml).

Fig. 3. Titration of 0.5 ml of 0.0932 N N₂H₄ with 0.074 N KMnO₄ in presence of 0.02 N H₂SO₄ and 1% NaF. (total volume ~10ml)

- A) no Cu SO₄ added
- B) 0.2ml 0.25 M CuSO₄
- C) 0.5 ml 0.25 M CuSO₄
- D) 2 ml 0.25 M CuSO₄
- E) 4 ml 0.25 M CuSO₄

TABLE 2 EFFECT OF CU_{SO}₄ CONCENTRATION

Titration of 0.5 ml 0.0932 N hydrazine with 0.074 N KMnO₄ in presence of 0.02 N H₂SO₄ and 5 ml 2% NaF. (Total volume ~10 ml).

Volume of 0.25 M CuSO ₄ (ml)	Vol. of KMnO ₄ consumed (ml)	Theoretical end point (ml)	Error (% ; ±)
-	0.33	0.63	-90.91 or 4.68 on basis of redn. of N ₂ H ₄ to NH ₂ .OH i.e. 2-electron.
0.2	0.573	0.63	9.47
0.5	0.63	0.63	nil
2	0.628	0.63	0.32
6	0.629	0.63	0.16

Effect of NaF Concentration: It is clear from Table 3 and Fig. 4, that results concordant with the theoretical with error less than 1% are obtained on using 0.8-1.5% NaF (corresponding to 4-7.5 ml of 2% NaF) in presence of 0.02N H₂SO₂ and 2 ml of 0.25N CuSO₄ per 10 ml).

TABLE 3 EFFECT OF NaF CONCENTRATION

Titration of 2 ml 0.0932 N N₂H₄ with 0.074 N KMnO₄ in presence of 0.02 N H₂SO₄ and 2 ml of 0.25 M CuSO₄. (Total volume 10 ml).

Volume of 2% NaF (ml)	Vol. of KMnO ₄ consumed (ml)	Theoretical end point (ml)	Error (% ; ±)
2	2.53	2.52	0.4
4	2.52	2.52	nil
6	2.52	2.52	nil
7.5	2.53	2.52	0.4

Fig. 4. Titration of 2 ml 0.0932 N N₂H₄ with 0.074 N KMnO₄ in presence of 0.02 N H₂SO₄ and 0.05 N CuSO₄ (total volum ~ 10 ml).
 A) 2ml of 2% NaF B) 4 ml of 2% NaF
 C) 6 ml of 2% NaF D) 7.5 ml of 2% NaF

Effect of Hydrazine concentration : The results for quantitative determination of different amounts of hydrazine under the optimum conditions of acidity, F⁻ ions and Cu⁺² ions concentration are shown in Table 4. and represented graphically in Fig. 5. It is obvious that amperometric titration of N₂H₄ with KMnO₄ is a satisfactory method for the quantitative determination of microamounts of N₂H₄ based on oxidation to N₂ and H₂O whereby permanganate is reduced to Mn(II). Amounts of N₂H₄ varying from 3.7 microgram to 5.97 milligram can be determined accurately.

Fig 5. Titration of hydrazine with KMnO₄ in presence of 0.02 N H₂SO₄, 1% NaF and 0.05 N Cu⁺² ions.

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|---|--|--------------|
| A) 0.5 ml 9.32 × 10 ⁻⁴ N N ₂ H ₄ ; | 74 × 10 ⁻⁴ N KMnO ₄ | Total volume |
| B) 3 ml 9.32 × 10 ⁻⁴ N N ₂ H ₄ ; | 7.4 × 10 ⁻⁴ N KMnO ₄ | 10 |
| C) 0.2 ml 9.32 × 10 ⁻³ N N ₂ H ₄ ; | 7.4 × 10 ⁻³ N KMnO ₄ | 20 |
| D) 0.5 ml 9.32 × 10 ⁻³ N N ₂ H ₄ ; | 7.4 × 10 ⁻³ N KMnO ₄ | 10 |
| E) 0.5 ml 9.32 × 10 ⁻³ N N ₂ H ₄ ; | 7.4 × 10 ⁻³ N KMnO ₄ | 10 |
| F) 2 ml 9.32 × 10 ⁻³ N N ₂ H ₄ ; | 7.4 × 10 ⁻³ N KMnO ₄ | 25 |
| G) 0.5 ml 0.932 N N ₂ H ₄ ; | 0.074 N KMnO ₄ | 20 |
| H) 2ml 0.0932 N N ₂ H ₄ ; | 0.074 N KMnO ₄ | 10 |
| I) 8 ml 0.0932 N N ₂ H ₄ ; | 0.074 N KMnO ₄ | 50 |

Discussion

Hydrazine is known to be oxidised quantitatively with KMnO₄ in acid solutions containing fluoride ions in presence of Cu⁺² ions as catalyst either visually or potentiometrically to yield N₂ and H₂O^{1,5} as follows :
 N₂H₄ + MnO₄⁻ + 2HF₂⁻ + 2H⁺ → N₂ + MnF₄⁻ + 4H₂O

TABLE 4 DETERMINATION OF DIFFERENT AMOUNTS OF HYDRAZINE

Titration of different concentrations of N₂H₄ with KMnO₄ in presence of 0.02 N H₂SO₄, 0.05 M CuSO₄ and 1.0 % NaF.

No.	Vol. & Normality of N ₂ H ₄ (ml)	Amounts of N ₂ H ₄ (mg)	Vol. & Normality KMnO ₄ consumed (ml)	Theor. end point (ml)	Error (% ±)	Total volume (ml)
1	0.5	9.32 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.632	7.4 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.63	0.32
2	3	9.32 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.75	7.4 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.78	0.71
3	0.2	9.32 × 10 ⁻³	0.253	7.4 × 10 ⁻³	0.252	0.39
4	0.5	9.32 × 10 ⁻³	0.633	7.4 × 10 ⁻³	0.63	0.48
5	0.5	9.32 × 10 ⁻³	0.628	7.4 × 10 ⁻³	0.63	0.32
6	2	9.32 × 10 ⁻³	2.51	7.4 × 10 ⁻³	2.52	0.40
7	0.5	0.0932	0.373	0.074	0.63	0.32
8	2	0.0932	1.793	0.074	2.52	0.40
9	8	0.0932	5.974	10.05	10.08	0.3

The amperometric titrations are of practical importance because of their simplicity and rapidity; the equivalence point can be determined from a few readings on each side of the end point. It is also not necessary to titrate slowly near the end point, whereas in the potentiometric titration, the equilibrium becomes sluggish as the concentration of the reactants decrease. KMnO_4 is reduced at almost zero applied e.m.f. as long as the solution contains reducible substances and it is not therefore necessary to apply an external e.m.f. Titration at zero applied potential is more advantageous because it is not necessary to deaerate the solutions before performing the titration since oxygen is not reduced under these conditions, contrary to the case when titrations are carried out at more negative potentials.

The titration curves obtained are nearly reversed L-shaped and the intersection of the two branches of the curve gives the end point. The amperometric method reveals the feasibility of determining N_2H_4 in amounts ranging from 3.7 μg to 5.97 mg accurately and is advantageous than the potentiometric procedure (the lower amount of N_2H_4 determined was 0.32 mg). The amperometric method can therefore be considered as a good analytical tool for microdetermination of hydrazine.

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